

humantech

D6.3 – HT Worker Assessment Report

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D6.3 - HT Worker Assessment Report

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Abstract

This deliverable summarises the sequential and ongoing evaluation of the HT wearables system and human-robot interactions. To identify the needs of the users at an early stage for incorporate them into the design process, an evaluation will be performed in a three-step approach. In this first deliverable the findings of a series of workshops held with workers and other type of stakeholders is presented. Based on the findings of Task 1.4 a lab-based approach was first carried out to evaluate usability, trust in automation and discomfort. At a further stage, objective assessment will be carried out by evaluation of physiological sensor data collected in dedicated training sessions.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
BVP	Blood Volume Pulse
CAD	Computer assisted design
CEIP	Center / College of Early Childhood and Primary Education, in Spanish
EEG	Electroencephalogram
F2F	Face-to-face
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GSR	Galvanic Skin Response
NASA-TLX	NASA Task Load Index
OSH	Occupational Safety and Health
TAMUX	Technology Acceptance Model based on User Experience
WMSD	Work-related musculoskeletal disorders
XR	Extended Reality

The HumanTech project

The European construction industry faces three major challenges: increase the safety and wellbeing of its workforce, improve its productivity, and become greener, making efficient use of resources.

To address these challenges, HumanTech proposes to develop **human-centred cutting-edge technologies** such as wearables for workers' safety and support and robots that can harmoniously coexist with human workers while contributing to the ecological transition of the sector.

HumanTech aims to achieve major advances in cutting-edge technologies that will enable a safe, rewarding, and digital work environment for a new generation of highly skilled construction workers and engineers.

These advances will include:

- **Robotic devices equipped with vision and intelligence** that allow them to navigate autonomously and safely in highly unstructured environments, collaborate with humans and dynamically update a semantic digital twin of the construction site in which they are.
- **Smart, unobtrusive workers protection and support equipment.** From exoskeletons activated by body sensors for posture and strain to wearable cameras and XR glasses that provide real-time workers' location and guidance for them to perform their tasks efficiently and accurately.
- An entirely new breed of **Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins (DSDTs) of construction sites** that simulate in detail the current state of a construction site at the geometric and semantic level, based on an extended Building Information Modelling (BIM) formulation that contains all relevant structural and semantic dimensions (BIMxD). BIMxDs will act as a common reference for all human workers, engineers, and autonomous machines.

The **HumanTech consortium** is formed by 22 organisations — leading research institutes and universities, innovative hi-tech SMEs, and large enterprises, construction groups and a construction SME representative — from 10 countries, bringing expertise in 11 different disciplines. The consortium is led by the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence's Augmented Vision department.

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1. Introduction

In this deliverable we present the results of a subjective assessment of the HT wearables system and human-robot interactions. This assessment has been completed by means of the organization of three different workshops with the main stakeholders involved in construction sector.

This deliverable presents the results of our work in task T6.2 (the subjective and objective assessment of worker's technology acceptance) of WP6 “Human Factors - Training and Usability Assessment”. Work on this task started at Month 6 of the project and has been executed in close collaboration with partners from the technical work packages WP4 “Wearable Technologies for Construction” and WP5 “Construction Robotics and Human-Robot Collaboration”.

The objective of the task is to provide a sequential and ongoing evaluation of the HT wearables system and human-robot interactions. The needs of the users will be identified at an early stage and incorporated into the design process. The evaluation will be performed in a three-step approach. Based on the contents developed in Task 1.4, the main technologies present in HumanTech and related to wearable devices and human-robot interaction have been identified. At a second stage, a lab-based approach is first carried out to evaluate usability, trust in automation and discomfort (in the approach of workshop being organized with the stakeholders). In the third stage, an objective assessment will be carried out by evaluation of physiological sensor data collected in dedicated training sessions (once the developments of WP4 and WP5 are mature enough and almost ready to be tested in pilots in WP7).

This deliverable is the first of two defining the HT Worker Assessment. The second and final version of assessment will be presented in Month 32 of the project in a new version of deliverable (D6.4). This first version includes:

[Chapter 2](#), which outlines the methodology used for the subjective evaluation of usability and user acceptance, based in a Design Thinking approach and explaining the technology assessment process.

[Chapter 3](#), which includes a full description of the technologies to be developed in HumanTech project and to be assessed in this process. The information presents the current situation in construction environment, the future technologies to be developed and the benefits of those technologies.

[Chapter 4](#), which presents the overall Focus Group sessions organization, together with the stakeholders' identification and definition. A whole procedure on how to run the Focus Groups (recruitment, session structure and GDPR compliance)

[Chapter 5](#), which is the result of the analysis of the data gathered in the three workshops organization.

[Chapter 6](#), which summarises the conclusions obtained from the data analysis made in Chapter 5.

2. Subjective evaluation of Usability and User acceptance

The use of advanced technology such as exoskeletons, smart glasses and wearable sensors can have a huge impact on the behaviour of the worker. Similarly, the use of robots on construction sites with human interaction is a major challenge. Although technologies are designed to support workers, they can have an opposite effect in the work environment especially when different technologies are combined. Workers may feel monitored, restricted in their movements or stressed by an information overload. In the context of a good work environment, special consideration should be given to the needs of workers. With the aforementioned in mind, BAUA and Tecnalia evaluated different HumanTech technologies with a focus on user requirements, acceptance and usability.

Figure 1: Workflow of the evaluation process

2.1. Design Thinking approach

The “Design Thinking” is a user-centred approach to innovation that draws from the designer's toolkit to integrate the needs of people, the possibilities of technology, and the requirements for business success [1]. The design thinking applies the way of thinking of the designer in order to match the users' needs with technologies and with business strategies that create added value for customers and business opportunities for suppliers.

Big companies like Apple or Google apply design thinking, as it is a way to create new idea and innovation it can be applied in any domain varying in the range of the development of products or services until the definition of processes or even for new business models. The sole limit to these applications could be the human imagination.

The design thinking follows a process where it can be identified 5 main features:

- **Create empathy**, the designer should be able to put themselves in the place of the end-user in order to understand their problems, needs and desires; and identify the solution the end-user is looking for.
- **Teamwork**, basically because the sum of all design analysis is greater of the parts.
- **Prototyping**, the Design Thinking wants to validate a solution before assuming that is the correct one. This is the aim of building prototype solutions before providing the final one.

- **Playful** needs to be promoted, it is about enjoying the process, and thanks to that, reaching a mental state in which people unleash their potential.
- **Visual and plastic content** must be applied, in this way creative and analytical minds are stimulated, resulting in innovative and feasible solutions.

Moreover, the Design Thinking is a process that includes 5 steps (see Figure 2). It is not a linear process; this means that at any moment we can go forward, backward or even jump one or more steps. Usually, it starts from collecting a lot of information, generating a large amount of content, which grows or decreases depending on the step in which you find yourself. Through the process this content will be refined until it converges to a solution that meets the objectives of the team or even exceed them.

Figure 2: Design Thinking methodology phases

2.2. Technology assessment process

A twofold approach will be followed in the evaluation of the human factors related to usability and user acceptance of HT innovations in the execution of technology assisted tasks, in the real working environment

Subjective assessment of the human factor related aspects will be performed with the use of scientifically validated questionnaires for lab and field research such as the System Usability Score, the NASA-TLX, etc. A questionnaire on Trust in Automation and further subjective measures based in proven models (such as TAMUX [5] and HEMEI **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**) to measure the acceptance degree of a worker, and also how it can be improved by the perceived usefulness will also be used. The aim will be to measure the hedonic (experiential) users' objectives and the experiential of

interaction (is based on meeting the psychological needs of users) to assess the user acceptance of robotic systems, taking into account operators' behavioural, cognitive and emotional responses. To gain user insights before potential users actually interact with the different technologies, expectations, foreseen task changes, opportunities, risk and the organisational relevance will be addressed in a first set of workshops. Here the stimulus material consist of a comprehensive presentation of the technology features and potential applications. The description of the specific measures used for the first user evaluation are presented in chapter 5.1.

The first subjective assessment results are being presented here in D6.3.

Objective evaluation: An objective perspective of user acceptance will be assessed by means of measurement of user's psychophysiological signals such as EEG (electroencephalogram), GSR (Galvanic Skin Response) and BVP (Blood Volume Pulse). This evaluation will be covered in the second version of this deliverable, D6.4 (to be delivered in M32, 2025).

3. Technologies to be assessed

In this section, information related to the different wearable and interactive technologies is presented (in a similar way as it has been presented to the participants in the Focus Groups).

3.1. Exoskeletons

3.1.1. Current situation: Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs)

Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) are the most common work-related health problem in Europe. Their origin is due to multiple causes. Except for processes originating solely from accidental injuries (over exertion), in almost all cases, several risk factors are involved in the production of MSDs, which are related to the task and to the organisation of work: manual handling of loads, forced static or dynamic postures, repetitive movements, etc.

Figure 3: Results of musculoskeletal symptom survey from 39 working bricklayers

Constructing a brick wall remains a labour-intensive task. It is a repetitive procedure in which part of the work is carried out in awkward postures, for example, when the work is done over shoulder height (the shoulders and elbows the main affected body areas).

3.1.2. Exoskeleton technologies

In recent years, exoskeletons have been proposed as the solution to all the problems associated with WMSDs. It was thought that by transferring the burdens of physically demanding work to these mechatronic devices, which follow and reinforce our every movement, we would become bionic superhumans, insensitive to the stresses of manual labour. But the promise of effortless work thanks to exoskeletons has not yet been realized in the real world. This is due to the inherent limitations of the technologies currently used in exoskeletons, i.e., it hinders other movements of the worker.

Figure 4: Proposed exoskeleton solution

3.1.3. Benefits of HumanTech exoskeleton

The exoskeleton would assist the wearer in its task ...

- Reducing the muscular activity of the assisted areas (i.e., while placing bricks over shoulder height)
- Preventing from adopting risk postures (i.e., overextension of the elbow when trying to reach far positions).

Figure 5: Situations in which exoskeleton should be **disabled**

... without impeding other movements involved in the tasks (leaning for a tool or mortar).

The human-exoskeleton interaction will be intelligent so that:

Figure 6: Situations in which exoskeleton should be **enabled**

- The exoskeleton anticipates and adapts to the needs of the user in each task (applying the necessary support at the necessary time) and,
- The exoskeleton gets out of the way when it is not needed (avoiding limiting or hindering other movements of the operator to increase acceptance)

3.2. Interactive robotics

3.2.1. **Current situation: isolated robotic systems**

Current robotic systems as a vital part of automated production lines are normally **isolated by physical barriers** and workers are not allowed to be around. But a new concept of **collaborative robots** safer for workers to be around during operation is arisen, as they often have integrated mechanisms for safe stop when a collision is detected before serious damage is done to a worker or property.

Figure 7: Human robot collaborative scenario

Figure 8: Workers transporting materials

Furthermore, in construction sites, multiple tasks, monotonous, dangerous or low productivity (e.g., transportation of materials from one place to another) are being accomplished.

3.2.2. Interactive robotics technologies

Interactive robotics technology allows for workers and robots sharing the task and executing it together at the same time. But still, the main drawback is that cobots still require significant advanced training to be operated and robot programming time can be a bottleneck for efficiency.

Figure 9: Collaborative robot example

Furthermore, the development of intuitive commu-

Figure 10: Human robot multimodal interaction

nication channels (as speech, gestures, etc.) between interactive / collaborative robot and worker can significantly contribute to efficient deployment of cobots in construction sites.

3.2.3. Benefits of HumanTech interactive robotics

HumanTech interactive Robotics technology can contribute to:

- Execution of supporting task (e.g., brick hand-over) allowing the worker to concentrate on core-competence tasks
- Execution of physically difficult tasks (e.g., moving heavy loads)
- Execution of time-consuming repetitive tasks (e.g., material handling)

But additionally, collaborative and interactive robotics allows for:

- Workers can safely work close to the robots
- Workers can use normal language and intuitive gestures for giving robots simple commands, no advanced robotic training required
- Workers understand behavior of the robot and are comfortable working with robots
- Robots behave in a predictable manner

Figure 11: Interactive robotics helping human

3.3. **XR Glasses**

3.3.1. **Current situation: visualization of 3D object in a 2D environment**

Currently, the visualization of 3D objects is made in a 2D screen of a laptop/tablet. In that case, CAD drawing can lead to misinformed CAD data

Furthermore, there is insufficient construction data and information available to the worker leading to inefficient decision making and errors.

Additionally, worker training scenarios normally are in dangerous and unsafe on-site locations.

Figure 12: Worker training in dangerous on-site locations

3.3.2. **XR Glasses technologies**

The solution proposed by HumanTech is based on Extended reality (XR) (a computer-based technology that adds virtual content to the real-world environment). Using these XR glasses like Microsoft HoloLens 2, 3D models and 2D elements like texts are superimposed onto the real world.

Figure 13: XR technologies for superimposed content

Mainly, in HumanTech, XR technology will be used for:

- Visualization
- Interaction with 3D models
- Training of workers in safe and remote environments

3.3.3. **Benefits of HumanTech XR Glasses**

The different XR functions are:

- Visualizing 3D objects
- Provide a user interface
- Work over 3D holograms or multi-user collaboration

Figure 14: XR used in construction sites

Engineers and industrial designers can visualize and collaborate with **CAD data** in an Augmented Reality environment.

4. Focus Group Session organization

4.1. Stakeholders Identification and definition

The objective of this first step is to identify which roles and people in the construction environment are going to be involved in the project and their level of influence. To analyse the environment in which we want to work, some actions are needed: to explore who are the involved people, the problems that exist, what are the priority needs and the capacity to cope with them.

In HumanTech, 3 types of relevant stakeholders have been identified: apprentices, workers and supervisors (site responsible person, engineer or OSH manager). Figure 15 shows the stakeholders' map and it reflects the connections between the different users that are involved in the overall scenario of the HumanTech solution and their environments.

In the organized focus groups, all type of stakeholders have been present: workers, site responsible, design engineers, responsible of risk and safety and apprentices.

Table 1: Stakeholders' description

Stk. Group	Motivations & Goals	Benefits from solution	Influence <i>High /medium /low</i>	Importance <i>High /medium /low</i>	Relations to others stk.
Apprentice	<p>Electricians and carpenters learning new technologies and methods.</p> <p>Minds are open to the process but also aware of robotics and digitisations.</p> <p>New working processes.</p> <p>Innovative working methods combined with the traditional practises,</p> <p>Low ability to influence change of new thinking on construction sites as they are new. The involvement of this stakeholder group is vital as they are the future of the construction industry and their ability to change is instrumental. Also, their tutors are very important here. Tutors and employers.</p> <p>Increased safety and healthy work conditions</p>	Safer environment resulting in less accidents, improved health of apprentice.	Medium	High	Worker
Worker	Increased safety and healthy work conditions	Safer environment resulting in less accidents, improved health of workers.	High	High	Supervisor, apprentice
	Activities like bending and lifting bricks and lintel could result in wear and tear on spine and nearby tissues which could result in problems like lower back pain,	Reduced number of physically demanding activities.	High	High	

	Flexibility and applicability of the robot in repetitive and tedious/hazardous activities/jobs.	Enhanced safety measures for the workforce, relieve workers from tedious/hazardous activities, more opportunities for human-robot collaboration.	Medium	High	
Supervisor (site responsible person, engineer or OSH manager)	Better utilization of resources like time, material and worker.	Productivity and efficiency increase, and shorter project lead time.	High	High	Worker
	Cost reduction and increase in overall profitability of the project	Increased competitive advantage.	High	Medium	
	Avoiding repetitive, hazardous and tedious activities increase health and safety of worksites.	Reduced labour turnover, less absenteeism, and better work planning and organization.	High	High	

4.2. How to run the Focus Groups

The interviews cover both the interests and values of users in terms of their thinking about specific issues (e.g., construction sector, technological components, digitalization), as well as concrete needs when it comes to how they interact with digital industrial solutions. In this project, it was decided to perform these interviews by organizing a set of focus groups by some of the partners involved in HumanTech project. A focus group is a small-group discussion guided by a moderator/s. It is used to learn about opinions on a designated topic, and to guide future action. In HumanTech case, we focused on the use of devices and technological components for construction sector, presented in section 3.

A set of questionnaires for each partner involved in the task has been prepared, and it can be used in several ways:

- **F2F focus groups:** the meetings have a moderator (a person from the partner involved in T6.2), which using as a basis the questionnaire promotes the brainstorming

of participants for each of the proposed questions. The moderator is in charge of collecting feedback and can also ask participants to complete the questionnaire individually after each question or after the meeting. We are targeting around 60-80 participants in total of which it is desirable to have female participants.

- **Remote focus groups:** It is the same format as the F2F focus group but via a conference call.

4.2.1. Recruiting and selecting participants

It is important to be sure that the participants belong to the targeted group of construction workers. As presented in the deliverable D1.3, based on a larger German employee survey, we were able to provide a sociodemographic characterisation of construction workers. The analysis has shown that the majority of workers are male and belong to the age range group between 50 and 60 years. Within HumanTech we aim at broadening the typical profile of our user group. Therefore, we aimed at participants with any gender and **within any range of age**. However, as we can assume that the basic population is unevenly distributed it will be a severe challenge to redistribute the specific samples according to our desired features.

Participants were recruited via the involved partners. The participation was voluntary and took place during a regular working /training hours.

4.2.2. Focus Group session structure

The focus group aims to gather qualitative insights from stakeholder perspectives. These qualitative insights will:

- Support the process of prioritizing the most relevant developments and interaction features for the project components.
- Support the further refinement of the project development interfaces.

We have selected the focus group as being appropriate methods because:

- They provide rich qualitative data.
- They can be carried out by non-specialists, after a training phase.
- It is not overly time-consuming.

These sessions are valuable when we want to determine attitude, beliefs, values, knowledge or any other subjective orientations or mental concern.

Before each meeting and considering the project and national legal and ethical requirements, the moderator asks each participant to sign a consent form. In general, the questionnaires do not need to gather personal information, only some general questions about **sociodemographic information**, such as **range of age, gender, ages of experience and digital competences**. Then, the moderator reviews the purpose of the focus group, the ground rules and the goals of the meeting while encouraging open participation. A script for it is provided as a guideline:

Good morning and welcome to our session. Thanks for taking the time to join us to talk about how you foresee the potential of existing components and digital solutions for construction sector. My name is XXXX and assisting me is XXXX. It is very important to understand your needs and demands as users so we can provide the most suitable solution in HumanTech adapted to your needs.

We want to know what you think, and your work might be improved. We are having discussions like this with several groups around Europe.

There are no wrong answers but rather different points of view. Please feel free to share your point of view even if it differs from what others have said. Keep in mind that we are just as interested in negative comments as positive comments.

You've probably noticed the microphone. We are recording the session because we don't want to miss any of your comments. People often say very helpful things in these discussions, and we can't write fast enough to get them all down.

We guarantee that:

- *All data will be processed in line with European and national data protection law.*
- *All data will be kept securely and destroyed in due course.*
- *It will be made available only to the members of the project Research Consortium and subcontractors and to the European Commission.*

We will be on a first-name basis today, and we won't use any names in our reports. You may be assured of complete confidentiality. Anyway, all personal data will be destroyed once it is no longer needed for research purposes. After the meeting, we will share a summary of the main findings.

Well, let's begin. Tell us your name and a bit about yourself.

After this introduction, the moderator begins to make a brief contextualization of construction industry and the solutions provided by HumanTech. An example of the workshop presentation can be seen in Annex I: Example for workshop presentation.

After that s/he starts with the discussion. A questionnaire will be provided to each participant to be used during the meeting and to be collected at the end of it with the participants' feedback. **The questionnaires can be translated to any language** and then, **those questionnaires, together with a summary with the main conclusions in English should be sent to TECNALIA**. The questionnaires are different for each stakeholders group (apprentice, worker and supervisor). An example of the questionnaires can be consulted in Annex II: Questionnaires for stakeholders.

4.2.3. GDPR compliance and Informed Consent

Participants in the experiments should be assured that data from these objective measures will be anonymized and will be used only to evaluate the technological solutions, not any given worker's performance. Volunteers will participate in these studies only after having given an **Informed Consent** (refer to Annex III: Informed Consent document, in accordance with local and international regulations on privacy and the use of human subjects).

For the worker evaluation an **ethical approval** was obtained by the external HumanTech ethical advisor. Furthermore, a data privacy concept was set up by the partners according to GDPR. It provides information on the following points:

- Which type of data will be obtained? (in our case a) personal data when collecting informed consent and for sociodemographic data; b) research data when collecting ratings of the HT technologies)
- Description of specific data (like when and how will they be collected in the process, which questionnaires and concepts are used)
- From whom will the data be collected (the specific persons and organisations collecting the data)
- Administration & processing of personal & research data
- Storage of personal & research data
- When will the personal & research data be deleted?
- Information on the informed consent/data privacy concept handed out to the participants

The data treatment will be done in the following way:

- Collection of the personal data (names on the informed consent and data privacy statement) on paper, store it safe and separately within Tecnalia's /TUS office building and say so in the documents.
- Sociodemographic data shall also be collected separately, on paper but different than the one with the name on, stored and handled the same way
- The collection of research data (the answers to the specific questions). In the case of a physical workshop, these research data will be collected on written paper.

In this way, we only have anonymised research data which makes processing simpler and we are using a GDPR compliant tool. The complete Informed Consent text could be consulted at Annex III: Informed Consent document.

5. Focus Group Session results

5.1. Description of measures

In the beginning of the HumanTech project (2022), the project team identified literature-based user requirements for the HT technologies interactive robots, exoskeletons and XR glasses as well as technology-unspecific requirements in relation to data privacy. These identified general user requirements were the basis to develop open and closed questions in order to collect industry and task specific insights from construction site employees. They will be described in the following.

All employees were asked to voluntarily state their age range, gender, years of working experience and position. Furthermore, the overall affinity for technology was assessed among all participants, measured with questions based on the Affinity for Technology Interaction Short Scale (ATI-S; Wessel, Attig & Franke, 2019). Those questions were answered on a 5-point scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). For employees belonging to the group of workers or apprentices, the closed questions furthermore addressed expectations in relation to the design principles as stated in the ISO standard ISO 9241-210:2019(en) "Ergonomics of human-system interaction — Part 210: Human-centred design for interactive systems". Each design principle (User error robustness, Self-descriptiveness, Conformity with user expectations, Suitability for individualisation, Suitability for the task, Learnability, Controllability) is represented by one item. This self-developed and shortened scale is based on the the Iso-Metrics questionnaire developed by Gediga and colleagues (Gediga, Hamborg & Dürtsch, 1999). The latest version of the

ISO standard has rephrased some of the design principles, nevertheless enable the here addressed interaction principles to analyse potential user expectations and preferences. These questions were answered on the same scale as the affinity for technology items but had one additional option if participants could not rate one specific item (0 = no idea). An interaction principle mean was calculated for each technology to gain insights in the overall expectations towards the three different technologies.

Additionally, participants were asked to rank the importance of different design considerations for each technology derived from literature (1 = least important to 8/9/10 = most important). Participants were asked to rank nine design considerations for interactive robots, examples were “I would like to use gestures to interact with the cobot” or “I would like to have control over the work rate (e.g. including the option to increase or decrease the speed as needed)”. For exoskeletons they were asked to rank eight design considerations, examples were “I need to be fast in my work, so I need something that I can move really fast with” or “I would like exoskeletons to be easy to clean and the possibility for sterilization”. Finally, participants were asked to rank 10 design considerations for XR glasses, examples were “I would like exoskeletons to be easy to clean and the possibility for sterilization” or “If I need to wear a helmet at work, I would like the XR glasses being attached to the helmet”.

The group of “responsible person /engineer /OSH manager” did not answer the questions on the specific design principles and design considerations but three closed, self-developed questions related to the organisational relevance of the technology. The questions were 1) I believe the implementation of interactive robots/exoskeletons/XR glasses in a company like [Acciona] is beneficial; 2) I believe it is sensible that the company invests in interactive robots/exoskeletons/XR glasses; 3) I believe the workforce will be open-minded towards inter-active robots/exoskeletons/XR glasses. Again, the questions were answered on a 5 point scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) and also included the possibility to choose 0 for “no idea”. Internal consistency was calculated for each technology scale. For the Organisational Relevance Robotics scale Cronbach’s Alpha was $\alpha = 0.1$. This value is not acceptable (Streiner, 2003). The item “I believe the workforce will be open minded towards cobots” yielded the lowest mean ($M = 2.50$; $SD = 1.05$). If the items was removed from the scale the internal consistency would increase to $\alpha = 0.5$. For the Organisational Relevance Exoskeletons scale $\alpha = 0.6$ was obtained, which is just acceptable (Streiner, 2003). For the XR glasses scale on Organisational Relevance $\alpha = 0.8$ was obtained, which is considered a very good value (Streiner, 2003).

Open questions for each technology included for instance the participant’s belief on how their working task will change under the use of the technology, expected benefits and problems (each in a short- and long-term) as well as most important resources needed for a successful implementation.

5.2. Descriptive data all workshops

Table 2 summarises the sociodemographic measures for all participants of the three workshops held in Spain and Ireland. A detailed description of each sample can be found in the according section. Data is presented in percentages and only given if the number is greater than 5% due to data privacy.

Table 2: Descriptive data of sociodemographic measures

Variable		Alicante (n = 22)	Zubieta (n = 27)	Limerick (n = 26)
Gender	female	14%	19%	
	male	86%	78%	100%
	other			
Age range	< 25	9%		85%
	between 26 and 35	23%	19%	12%
	between 36 and 45	27%	37%	
	between 46 and 55	32%	30%	
	> 56	9%	11%	
Years of expereince	<= 5	19%	11%	92%
	between 6 and 10			
	> 10	81%	85%	
Position	worker	45%	56%	92%
	responsible person /engineier /OSH manager)	55%	44%	8%
Affinitiy for technology mean (whole sample)		4,0	3,8	3,0
Affinitiy for technology SD (whole sample)		0,7	0,7	0,7

5.3. Focus Group at Acciona (Alicante - Spain)

5.3.1. Place & Participants

The first organized workshop was a physical one and it took place on 16th May 2023 in CEIP (Center / College of Early Childhood and Primary Education, in Spanish) La Paz/ELX in Torrellano (Alicante, Spain).

Participants were recruited by Acciona among the stakeholders working in the construction site (workers and supervisors). A total of 22 participants took part in this first physical workshop, organized in Acciona premises.

Figure 16: Different works to be done in the construction site

The construction site refers to the construction project of an Infant, primary and secondary education center in Torrellano (Alicante). The educational center **is organized in two buildings:**

- Main building, which contains all the dependencies of the classroom, administration, general services and complementary uses. In its internal organization, the main building is divided into two levels: a) The ground floor (contains the main entrances) and b) the upper floor (contains practically all of the educational units).
- Gym, intended exclusively for the indoor sports room, monitor, toilets, changing rooms, storage rooms and facilities room.

Figure 17: Construction site map & main accesses

Both buildings are connected by means of a pergola.

The **works to be carried out** will be mainly: demolitions, earth movements, foundations (solved by making footings and predicted structure of reinforced concrete and composed of slabs), partitions (dry projected, by means of a self-supporting framework on concrete pillars), facade enclosure (with facing brick), installation sanitation (registrable chests), installation of plumbing and sanitary devices, electrical installation and lighting,

heating installation and fuel tank, gas installation, air treatment installation (air conditioning), photovoltaic installation and fire protection installation.

The **machinery planned to be used** will include (among others): compressors, excavator (wheel and track), backhoe loader (combined machine), electropneumatic hammer, concrete trucks, tower crane, lift truck, truck mounted concrete pump, irrigation tub, lifting platform, forklift, electric concrete mixer, stone-ceramic material cutter, vibrator, radial, fixed nail gun, portable drill, electric wall chaser, polyurethane spraying machine, chainsaw, polishers, cast torch for asphalt blankets and hand power tools.

5.3.2. Focus Group organization

The workshop was organized in three different sessions, each of them lasting one hour and a half, approximately.

The procedure is described in section 4.2. Furthermore, a recording of the discussions was done (in order to compile all the insights from the participants).

Figure 18: Focus groups sessions in Alicante (Spain)

Written questionnaires were collected and analysed afterwards. Results of the findings are presented in the following section.

5.3.3. Focus Group findings Alicante

5.3.3.1 Sample description

The sample from the Alicante workshop included 22 participants. More than 80% of the participants were male and the majority of the participants was found in the age group between 36 and 45 (27 %) and between 46 and 55 (32 %). Most participants (> 80 %) had 10 years or more of working experience in the construction sector. 45 % of the participants were worker, 55 % of this sample had an engineering or OSH managing position. Results for the affinity for technology show that both groups, worker ($M = 3.7$; $SD = 0.9$) and persons responsible ($M = 4.2$; $SD = 0.5$), show slightly higher values than the scale

average. In this sample, persons responsible show higher values in the overall affinity of technology compared to worker.

5.3.3.2 *Missing values*

In the Alicante workshop quite a large number of missing values in the sample is visible. For the preference items 40 % of the participants did not give any answers. In many cases, the open questions were only answered by on word “yes”, “no”, “of course”. Furthermore, in some cases participants even express their difficulties in commenting on the questions “I don't know”, “I am not interested”. Interpretations of collected results therefore must be considered against these findings.

5.3.3.3 *Results user expectations interaction principles*

Overall, participants in the Alicante worksite had the highest expectations towards interactive robotic systems ($M = 3.8$; $SD = 0.7$). Lowest expectations were stated towards the interaction design of XR glasses ($M = 3.5$; $SD = 1.3$). For interactive robots, potential users have the highest expectations on the interaction principles *Suitability for the task*, *Learnability* and *Controllability*. For exoskeletons, participants expect *Suitability for individualisation* the most, followed by *Suitability for the task*. For XR glasses, participants see *Controllability* as the most important interaction principle. **¡Error! No se encuentra**

el origen de la referencia. depicts the expected interaction principles for the Alicante sample and the three addressed technologies.

Figure 19 User expectation interaction principles- workshop Alicante; Scale 1 = strongly disagree (low expectations) – 5 = strongly agree (high expectations)

5.3.3.4 Results on organisational relevance

Participants holding a managing or site responsible position were also asked to judge the organisational relevance for each of the HumanTech technologies. In the Alicante sample twelve persons gave answers on the organisational relevance. Answering means are presented in figure 20. The participants slightly rate exoskeletons the highest in terms of organisational relevance ($M = 3.8$; $SD = 0.59$), very closely followed by XR glasses ($M = 3.7$; $SD = 0.77$) and interactive robots ($M = 3.6$; $SD = 0.77$). A t-test reveals, there are no significant differences noticeable. Neither between interactive robots and exoskeleton, $t(11) = -1.06$, $p = .312$, interactive robots and XR glasses, $t(11) = -0.52$, $p = .615$, nor exoskeletons and XR glasses, $t(11) = 0.42$, $p = .684$.

Figure 20 Organisational relevance Alicante; Scale 1 = strongly disagree (low organisational relevance) – 5 = strongly agree (high organisational relevance)

5.3.3.5 Qualitative results

Qualitative data on challenges, opportunities and general considerations were also collected. Overall participants reported more challenges than opportunities in relation to all three technologies. In terms of interactive robot, supervisors see especially the given *Suitability for the task* as a potential challenge as reasons they name the uniqueness of construction tasks and the complexity of the specific brick layering task. Compared to industrial task, construction tasks are less repetitive, especially from a technical manipulation perspective, therefore making automation efforts especially difficult. Furthermore, the navigation capabilities, height limitations and the battery life are seen as major challenges to overcome in order to achieve sufficient task execution. Hence, participants question the basic functionalities of the interactive robot. Lastly, spatial considerations in a construction environment are vital. Interactive robots occupy physical space, and their presence may hinder the movement of human workers or interfere with existing work processes. Optimising robotic designs to minimize spatial impact and maximize manoeuvrability therefore seems essential. Potential challenges in relation to interactive robots addressed by workers, which are also commonly reported in scientific literature. Firstly, they criticise that if task allocation solely takes robotic abilities into consideration, preferable parts of the task will be

automated (P₁: [...] *"the cobot performs the easy part of their job (for example, placing the bricks)."*)

Secondly, they see the possible risk that once parts of the brick-layering task are automated by the robotic system, only residual tasks remain with the worker. Workers even report having to constantly correct robotic manipulation actions due to the uniqueness of each work piece (brick) handled is also foreseen as a possible risk (P₁: [...] *"because the bricks are not exactly the same and in the end the worker will have to adjust the bricks manually."*).

The potential **risk of deskilling**, especially in an early on the job learning phase is also addressed by the workers, which eventually could lead to a decreased situation awareness for the task (P₂: *"The problem is that this trade must be learned from the beginning, with all the tasks that it entails. If an apprentice already starts with a robot and is only going to learn to do one thing."*). Similar to the group of supervisors, the workers state reluctance towards **robotic capabilities** for a number of relevant tasks (P₃: [...]. *The "fine" work will always have to be the operator's."*). Nevertheless, the worker also raises the **fear of job loss** in relation the robotic system.

For exoskeletons, the open discussion has brought forward more opportunities than for interactive robots. Though supervisory as well as worker also outline a number of challenges in relation to exoskeletons. Supervisors see the main purpose for exoskeletons mostly with the jobs of installers for example when placing pipes or electricity lines. The issue of **technology acceptance** is also touched. One supervisor states the importance of perceived benefit from using the exoskeleton in order to enhance acceptance. A second statement brings forward the argument that if exoskeletons were for example mandatory like personal protective equipment (PPE), the supervisor believes there would not be any acceptance problems. This assumption however is regarded as hasty. Research on technology acceptance in relation to exoskeletons rather suggest overall reluctance toward the technology. The workers show general interest and openness towards

the technology of exoskeletons. It is stated that exoskeletons are “*the most interesting of all technologies*”. However, this result might also be explained by the mere unfamiliarity with the technology, which also becomes evident in the statements (P₄: [...] “*an exo for the kidneys*”)¹.

Apart from the mentioned opportunities, the supervisors do name a number of challenges associated with the use of exoskeletons. They raise **feasibility concerns**: supervisors express doubts about the implementation of exoskeletons in the near future on construction worksites. Furthermore, they express concerns related to sensors performance. The harsh environment of construction sites demands exoskeletons to be equipped with shockproof and dustproof sensors to ensure proper functioning and safety. Supervisors also raise the question of cost allocation. There is uncertainty about whether the main company or the subcontractors should bear the cost of purchasing the exoskeletons. If subcontractors cover the expense, they may pass it on to the main company. Workers report that they already had a previous unsuccessful test of exoskeletons at the company. They attributed the failing to the challenging and dirty work environment, and workers' **discomfort** in wearing the technology for long durations (8 hours). Here participants see the need for a user-centred technology evaluation based on a physical strain analysis. It remains to be evaluated which body parts experience the highest strain after wearing the exoskeleton to further assess potential risks and benefits. However, workers do see the need for improved a workplace design. They mention the example of assembling scaffolding which has led to a number of injuries in the past. In relation to exoskeletons maintenance, it is seen as an issue. Workers are concerned with the **maintenance** of exoskeletons, seeking clarification on how it will be managed to ensure effective and safe operation. Furthermore, they specifically name the risk of entanglement. The issue is raised, that the exoskeleton might get caught on external elements, potentially leading to entanglement and hazardous situations, posing safety apprehensions.

¹ This could also be an error due to translation activities and referring to the body region of kidneys, thus targeting the lower back.

Regarding XR glasses, supervisors and workers both rather see their application for visualising remote workplaces, for example video pictures provided by a robotic application in a pipe. Another application would be showing construction site simulations, either for training purposes or for showing customers a specific worksite. However, the transferability from a simulated construction site to a real one is seen critical.

5.4. Focus Group at Acciona (Zubieta - Spain)

5.4.1. Place & Participants

The second organized workshop was a physical one and it took place on 15th June 2023 in New Penitentiary Center of San Sebastián (Gipuzkoa-Spain). The construction site is in the settlement of Zubieta, belonging to the municipality of San Sebastián and located to the southwest of it. The plot is located on the so-called “Ezkuzaitzeta Hill”, near the Autovía del Norte (N-I), on the edge of the Zubieta neighborhood, and also close to the Oria riverbed.

Figure 21: Location of Zubieta construction site

Participants were recruited by Acciona among the stakeholders working in the construction site (workers and supervisors). A total of 27 participants took part in this second physical workshop, organized in the Acciona offices at construction site.

The penitentiary center **is made up of a series of buildings with different uses**, depending on the function they fulfill within the center. Some of these buildings are: access control, kennels, social integration center, kitchens, laundries and facilities, communications and coexistence, services headquarters, sports-cultural center and nursing among others.

The **works to be carried out** will be mainly: earthworks, demolitions, foundations (by footings and by piling), execution of concrete walls, roofs, exterior enclosures and facades, partitions, interior partitions and masonry, installation of electricity, telecommunications and security, installation of ventilation and air conditioning, among others...

The **machinery planned to be used** will include (among others): scaffolding, formwork systems, circular saw, vibrator, electric concrete mixer, motor grader, vibratory compactors, pneumatic compressor and hammer, electric and portable hand tools, drill and chainsaw.

5.4.2. Focus Group organization

The workshop was organized in four different sessions, each of them lasting one hour and a half, approximately.

The procedure is described in section 4.2. Furthermore, a recording of the discussions was done (in order to compile all the insights from the participants).

Written questionnaires were collected and analysed afterwards. Results of the findings are presented in the following section.

Figure 22: Focus groups sessions in Zubieta (Spain)

5.4.3. Focus Group findings Zubieta

5.4.3.1 *Sample description*

The workshop, which took place in the Acciona location Zubieta included 27 participants. The majority of participants were male (78 %) and most belonged to the age group between 36 and 45 (37 %), a third of the participants was aged between 36 and 55 years. A large number of persons stated more than 10 years of working experience (85 %). In this sample, 56 % of the participants were worker, 44 % held an engineering or OSH managing position. Results for the affinity for technology show similar values for workers ($M = 3.7$; $SD = 0.7$) and person responsible ($M = 3.8$; $SD = 0.7$). Both groups are just slightly above average.

5.4.3.2 *Results user expectations interaction principles*

At the Zubieta worksite participants had the highest expectations in terms of the interaction principles towards XR glasses ($M = 3.8$; $SD = 1.1$), followed by exoskeletons ($M = 3.7$;

$SD = 1.0$). They had the lowest expectations regarding interactive robots ($M = 3.4$; $SD = 0.7$). For interactive robots, participants had the highest expectations towards *Controllability*, followed by *Suitability for the task* and *Conformity with user expectations* likewise. With regards to exoskeletons, potential users in the Zubieta construction site mostly expect the interaction principle *Suitability for individualisation* and *Conformity with user expectations* likewise, followed by *Controllability*. For XR classes the most important interactions principles for this sample are *Learnability* followed by *Suitability for the task* and thirdly *Self-descriptiveness*. The overall interaction principles results for the three HumanTech technologies for the Zubieta sample are presented in Figure 23.

Figure 23: User expectation interaction principles- workshop Zubieta; Scale 1 = strongly disagree (low expectations) – 5 = strongly agree (high expectations)

5.4.3.3 Results on organisational relevance

Onsite OSH manager rated the organisational relevance of the three assisting technologies. 8 people rated the organisational relevance. On a descriptive level XR glasses ($M = 4.8$; $SD = 0.24$) are rated with the highest organisational relevance to the participants, whereas interactive robots ($M = 3.8$; $SD = 0.47$) show the lowest values. There is no statistical significant difference observable for organisational relevance between interactive robots and exoskeleton, $t(7) = -0.46$, $p = .662$. However, there is a statistical significant difference observable between interactive robots and XR glasses, $t(7) = -4.92$, $p = .002$, and also between exoskeletons and XR glasses, $t(7) = -2.47$, $p = .043$. XR glasses. The re-

sults indicate that organisational relevance is seen stronger for XR glasses than for interactive robots and exoskeletons. Results on organisational are presented in Figure 24 Organisational relevance Zubieta; Scale 1 = strongly disagree (low organisational relevance) – 5 = strongly agree (high organisational relevance).

Figure 24 Organisational relevance Zubieta; Scale 1 = strongly disagree (low organisational relevance) – 5 = strongly agree (high organisational relevance)

5.4.3.4 Qualitative results

Within the Zubieta sample, qualitative data was collected on overall risks and opportunities in relation to interactive robots, exoskeletons and XR glasses. Additionally, participants were able to give global comments on the three technologies. Altogether, participants in the Zubieta sample had fewer comments in relation to the addressed topics, compared to the Alicante sample. Likewise, to the Alicante sample, most of the comments were directed towards interactive robots and exoskeletons. Opportunities for the use of interactive robots are seen in relation to the working task. Especially for **indoor applications**, like indoor tile laying or for **heavy lifting**. Here benefits are seen if interactive robots assist lifting heavy loads upstairs or onto scaffolding. It is also noted, that as interactive robots should be reconfigured for different task an external supplier is needed in order to handle all **task configurations**, ensuring adaptability. At the same time, there are a number of potential risks and challenges raised by the participants in relation to interactive robots. Firstly, **environmental complexity and obstacles** are

seen as a challenge. Not only does the irregular and dynamic nature of the construction work environment complicate the introduction of robots, but further poses worksite obstacles challenges for robots to navigate and interact effectively. Secondly, participants consider **task performance** critical. Interactive robots require standardised processes and specialised adaptations to different tasks, which may not be feasible for all many construction workers to cope. Adapting and programming interactive robots for various tasks might potentially lead to delays and inefficiencies. In addition, it is stated that the mere presence of the interactive robot might hinder workers in performing other tasks that require manual dexterity or flexibility. Furthermore, participants foresee the risk of **shared operator awareness** in relation to the robotic system. The systems are viewed as an additional responsibility, which requires additional attention. In addition, the **proximity** of humans to the interactive robots are brought up as a concern, especially in relation to safety. Finally, the fear of job loss is brought forward here. Participants do see the threat of interactive robots leading to job losses, as they might gradually replace human workers.

5.5. Focus Groups at Limerick (Ireland)

5.5.1. Place & Participants

The Irish workshop took place on Friday morning June 23rd 2023 in Limerick Ireland, delivered by TUS staff Gloria Callinan and Martin Breen to apprentice electricians and carpenters at the Raheen training centre campus of the Limerick Clare Education and Training Board.

Figure 25: Limerick Clare Education and Training Board premises

The workshop was attended by 26 construction apprentice participants and 4 tutors.

Limerick and Clare Education and Training Board is the state education and training authority for the Limerick and Clare region. It is one of 16 statutory regional education authorities established by the Education and Training Boards Act 2013.

It delivers educational services to over 34,000 students/learners across the region annually and has responsibility for:

- 3 Community National Schools,
- 18 Community Colleges,
- 28 Further Education and Training Colleges/Centres and works with community groups in almost 300 locations across the region².

5.5.2. Focus Group organization

Through long established local working relationships in the region and connections with the VET centre in Limerick (Limerick Clare Education and Training Board), operating as a Centre of Excellence in NZEB and retrofit, TUS were in a position to organise the focus

Figure 26: Focus groups sessions in Limerick (Ireland)

group working in collaboration with the VET centre management. TUS also has a campus in Limerick city.

Powerpoint slides were prepared in advance by task leader Tecnalia and the presentation was co-delivered by TUS team members Gloria Callinan and Martin Breen.

5.5.3. Focus Group findings

5.5.3.1 *Sample description*

The third workshop took place in Limerick, Ireland and here 30 persons participated in the workshop. 26 apprentice data sets can be included in the further analysis. In this sample, all participants were male and the majority was aged under 25 (85 %) and stated

² [Home | Limerick and Clare Education and Training Board \(lcteb.ie\)](https://www.lcetb.ie/)

to have under 5 years of working experience (92 %). In this sample most persons were apprentices (92 %). In this sample participants show an average level affinity for technology ($M = 3,0$; $SD = 0,7$), and the lowest value in all three workshops.

5.5.3.2 **Results user expectations interaction principles**

Overall, the Irish sample of mostly apprentices had the highest expectations towards exoskeletons ($M = 3.2$; $SD = 1.2$), followed by XR glasses ($M = 2.9$; $SD = 1.2$) and interactive

Figure 27: User expectation interaction principles- workshop Limerick; Scale 1 = strongly disagree (low expectations) – 5 = strongly agree (high expectations)

botics ($M = 2.9$; $SD = 1.0$), with nearly no descriptive difference between the two technologies. Towards interactive robots, participants had the highest expectations regarding the interaction principle of *Self-descriptiveness* and *Controllability* likewise, followed by the principle of *Conformity with user expectations*. For exoskeletons, participants have the highest expectations towards *Learnability*, secondly towards *Self-descriptiveness* and thirdly towards *Controllability*. With regards to XR glasses, the Limerick participants mostly expect the technology to show high *Learnability*, followed by *Self-descriptiveness* and thirdly by *Controllability*. The overall interaction principles result for the three HumanTech technologies for the TUS sample are presented in Figure 27.

5.6. Combined analysis

In order to obtain a broader picture on the expectations of interaction principle as well as employees' attitude towards the different HumanTech technologies combined analysis were performed. Overall user expectations regarding the interaction principles for all technologies were compared between the three samples. Open-ended questions were used to assess the overall attitude towards the different technologies including expected task changes, expected benefits and problems. In many cases given answers very short, sometimes only stating one word. Therefore, the three different locations will be treated as one sample in order to analyse the qualitative attitudes. For a first clustering of the answers of the open-ended attitude items, the natural language processing tool ChatGpT³ was used. The clusters were then further reviewed and analysed. Based on expert verdict categories were reviewed for plausibility and either reduced or complemented by additional categories. Descriptive and inferential statistics were done using IBM SPSS Version 29.

5.6.1. **Comparison of expected interaction principles between different locations**

In order to compare the overall expectations in relation to the interaction principles the mean expectation score was calculated for each technology and the three different samples. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to assess if there were any differences between the three evaluation locations and the assessed technologies. According to Shapiro-Wilk test, a deviation from the normal distribution of the data was observed for the overall expectations on exoskeletons ($p < .05$) and XR glasses ($p < .05$) in the Zubieta location. Homogeneity of variances was asserted using Levene's Test which showed that equal variances could be assumed for interactive robots ($p = .593$), exoskeletons ($p = .240$) as well as XR glasses ($p = .417$). Due to the fact, that assumptions of normality were violated in two cases and samples sizes largely differ between the evaluation samples, Welch's ANOVA is reported. For interactive robotic systems the level of expectations in relation to the given technology differed statistically significant for the different evaluation sites, Welch's $F(2, 26) = 4.84$, $p = .016$. For expectations related to XR glasses there was also a significant difference noticeable between the different evaluation samples Welch's $F(2, 23) = 3.75$, $p = .039$. No significant difference was observed for exoskeletons Welch's

³ <https://chat.openai.com/>

$F(2, 24) = 1.25, p = .305$. For interactive robots, Games-Howell post-hoc analysis revealed a significant difference ($p = .019$) between the evaluation sites Alicante and Limerick (-.897, 95%-CI[-1.66, -0.136]). For XR glasses Games-Howell post-hoc analysis revealed a significant difference ($p = .023$) between the evaluation sites Zubieta and Limerick (-.907, 95%-CI[-1.708, -0.110]). The overall comparison of expectations towards the addressed Human-Tech technologies between the three samples is presented in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..**

Figure 28 Comparison of user expectations across three workshops; Scale 1 = strongly disagree (low expectations) – 5 = strongly agree (high expectations)

5.6.2. Overall attitude towards HumanTech technologies

Participants were asked, whether they believe, their working task would change through the use of an interactive robot, exoskeleton and XR glasses. Furthermore, they were asked to state potential benefits from their point of view as well as foreseen challenges, each in the short- and long-term.

5.6.2.1 Expected task changes

In relation to interactive robots answers were clustered into three categories: **Positive task changes, neutral or uncertain about task changes** and **negative or sceptical task changes**. Examples for positive task changes were: “It will help my work.”; “It will make life easier.”; “Task made easier.” Examples for the neutral category were: “I don’t know.”;

"I couldn't tell without trying."; "I can't imagine." For the negative or sceptical category, the following examples represent the cluster: *"Not much."; "It will be slower and more time-consuming."* Overall, the majority of answers indicate a positive view. Within the positive cluster, it becomes obvious, that participants expect the interactive robot to especially improve efficiency, reduce physical strain, awkward posture and to handle repetitive and dangerous tasks. Participants, who raise concerns, especially express scepticism regarding the aspect of *Suitability for the task* [...] *"more time consuming";* believe robot to [...] *"be inefficient".*

For the question how exoskeletons potentially change the working task, 5 clusters could be derived from the material. The first one contains **positive attitudes** towards potential task changes and **clear physical benefits** (e. g. *"Help for physical effort"; "improvement"; "increased speed and decrease fatigue"*). The second cluster specifically relates to **injury avoidance** (e. g. *"Avoiding injuries from repetitive tasks"; "Avoiding fatigue"; "Avoid injuries"*). To some degree, there is some overlap with the first cluster. However, considering the first two clusters, the majority of participants receive the exoskeleton as positive and expect many physical benefits. The third cluster describes doubts and uncertainty in relation to task changes and exoskeletons (e. g. *"Not clear for me."; "I don't think it will change anything."; Maybe it's a hindrance"*). The fourth category holds answers on **physical concerns** and the **Suitability for the task**. Here fewer answers can be found than in the positive attitudes cluster. Examples are: *"Too bulky and hard to get into tight areas"; "physically restricted"; [...] "muscles, it may degenerate"*. The final cluster of answers, the category of specific tasks, includes answers where participants have named specific tasks, where they specifically see a useful application of the exoskeleton (e. g. *"working overhead, pulling, pushing [...]; "Drilling above shoulder height may be easier"*).

Answers on possible task changes in relation to the use of XR glasses were clustered into two categories. Most answers fell under the first category, positive impact – better visualisation and efficiency. Here participants name a number of benefits they associate with the use of XR glasses like *"it would improve speed", "I will have more information", "more precision", "visualizing the work"*. The remaining answers were summarised under the category neutral – uncertain (*"No change"; "I don't know"; "Not good"*).

5.6.2.2 *Expected benefits*

When specifically asked for precise benefits most participants did not state any specific benefit to one of the addressed technologies. For all three technologies, most participants seem to see positive effects in the short-term, as well as in the long-term. However, only a few answers yielded benefits that are more specific. In relation to interactive robots, participants do expect **health improvements** through a reduction of injuries and a reduction in physical workload, especially in the long-term. For exoskeletons, there is a specific cluster on **injury prevention and musculoskeletal benefits** evident. Similar to the answers in relation to task changes, participants state here that they do see positive effects on the reduction of physical strain, musculoskeletal injuries and disorders. For the technology of XR glasses participants name the specific benefits of worker training, learning and skill development. Furthermore, they see benefits in the specific application of XR glasses for prototyping as well as in the design and planning phase, also through visualisation of future on-site activities.

5.6.2.3 *Expected challenges*

Participants were also asked where they see potential problems in the short- and long-term in relation to the HumanTech technologies. In general, the participants named challenges in a more nuanced way than benefits. For interactive robots they again raise the issue of suitability for the task, as it is seen that many construction tasks seem to be unique and complex to easily be automated by a robot. Furthermore, participants raise the concern of a very **unstructured environment** and difficult terrains. In addition, the lifetime of the robotic battery is questioned as well as **maintenance** in general. This is seen as a major challenge. Here also the issue of system integration, programming and much needed skilled personnel is addressed. Additionally, it is stated that low acceptance, mistrust or low technology acceptance could be potential challenges, as well as an unintuitive human-robot interaction. Lastly, complying with safety regulations in an appropriate way is considered an obstacle.

With regards to exoskeletons answers can be clustered into different categories. A number of participants name concerns regarding **comfort & mobility** (e. g. "*incompatibility with tasks*"; "*awkward movements*"; "*uncomfortable to wear*"; "*bulky and slow*"). Related to this aspect is the category **unstructured environment**. Again, workers state, that they do not see the technology suitable for outdoor work (e. g. "*limited application for construction tasks*"; "*not ideal for outdoor work*"). They also raise some issues related to

safety and physical health (e. g. *“possible injury if it fails with heavy loads”; “muscle atrophies with continued use”; “possible muscle weakening”; “Risk of misuse and injury”*). Furthermore, the aspect of **maintenance and reliability** are mentioned. Participants question how hygiene is insured, how reliable the technology is under harsh weather conditions and how breakdowns and malfunctions are handled. Another challenge that is brought forward by the participants is the aspect of worker perception and acceptance (e. g. *“Negative perception from workers”; “Privacy concerns”; Lack of support and acceptance”*). Further areas, which are according to the participants prone to be a source of challenges are **economic factors** (e. g. *“expenses of exoskeleton”; “uncertainty in economic benefits”*) as well as the need for **training**.

For XR glasses also a number of challenges are given. A number of potential challenges named by the participants relate to **technical issue** of the XR glasses (e. g. *“durability and fragility of the smart glasses”; “Battery life”; “Vision problems, focus and glare issues”*). Furthermore, a number of **health and safety** concerns were raised. First, emerging risks of falling or tripping *“potential accidents like walking into obstacles, running into barriers, or falling materials”*. But also risks in relation to eye sight (e. g. *“Eye strain, discomfort, or potential damage to eyes, especially when worn for long”; “blue light damage to eyes”*). Similar to the other technologies, participants do not entirely see XR glasses suited for construction worksite environments, question the required training, the development of a fitted software as well as reluctance from co-workers.

5.7. Discussion

The overall aim of the worker evaluation was to involve potential users at an early stage of technology and use-case development. Here the challenge arises that at this early stage potential users are not able to actually interact and use the technology for the specific task in question. To overcome this challenge, workers were shown the HumanTech technologies (interactive robots, exoskeletons and XR glasses) and gained insights in where and how to use these assisting technologies in the use cases in three onsite workshops. Potential workers were asked to rate their expectations regarding the interaction principles of all three technologies, expected task changes, benefits and challenges. Managing positions were also able to rate the organisational relevance.

5.7.1. **User expectations towards HumanTech technologies**

It is noteworthy that in the two Spanish samples (Alicante & Zubieta) participants expect all three assistive technologies to be more user-centred. At both worksites, the majority

of workers held 10 years or more of working experience, while the Limerick sample almost exclusively consisted of apprentices. This finding, that more experience worker have higher expectations regarding the interaction principles of innovative technologies is consistent with previous research findings. As reported by Funk et al. (submitted for publication), experienced and inexperienced users have different expectations towards interactive robots. This is particularly evident in the interaction principle of *Suitability for the task* and *Self-descriptiveness*. Experienced users rate both principles as significantly more important than inexperienced users. As stated by Funk et al., one reason why more experienced users have higher expectations towards the interaction principles in general and towards the principle of *Suitability for the task* in particular might be found in a prior experienced technology-driven development or implementation processes of a new system. This could have led to negative consequences like frustration or additional mental workload. In line with the findings reported by Funk et al., in the Alicante and the Zubieta sample the principle of *Suitability for the task* has been rated as one of the most important design principles in terms of the quantitative assessment. In contrast, the Limerick sample does not see *Suitability for the task* amongst the top three. The analysis of the qualitative data further reveals that, on a broader level, participants do see benefits from the technologies. However, once considered very practical for their various construction tasks, it becomes evident that there is reluctance as to whether the technologies will actually be able to perform the task in question sufficiently. Especially in relation to interactive robots, it is repeatedly stated that the system should not be too slow, has to be able to navigate in unstructured environments, dirty and harsh weather conditions and needs to have a reliable battery. Participants are very aware of the fact that many of the construction tasks, which seem repetitive for the human worker, are complex and unstandardised from a technology point of view.

5.7.2. Organisational relevance of HumanTech technologies

Employees holding an OSH responsible or managing position were asked to rate the organisational relevance for the different HumanTech technologies. The results from the managers in Alicante showed no statistically significant difference for the organisational relevance of the three technologies. However, on a descriptive level, the highest relevance was found for exoskeletons. Differences in the organisational relevance of the technologies were found in the Zubieta sample. Participants at the Zubieta site were convinced that investing in XR glasses and their implementation would be more bene-

ficial for the company and that workers will be more open minded towards the technology compared to exoskeletons and XR glasses. At the Zubieta worksite, workers also had the highest expectations towards the interaction principles of XR glasses.

For interactive robots in particular, the item analysis of to the organisational relevance scale shows, that while managers believe that a company's investment in interactive robots is sensible, they do not believe that employees are open to the technology. This is not the case for exoskeletons and XR glasses. Here, too, investment is seen as beneficial and a greater openness to the technologies is assumed. This impression is to some degree supported by the qualitative data.

5.7.3. Risks & benefits of HumanTech technologies

When considering potential risks, benefits and task changes associated with the three technologies it becomes evident, that participants strongly focus on physical workload and strain, injuries and accidents, which is not surprising in this work environment and puts a spotlight on one of the main issues to tackle. There are fewer points addressed by the participants, which relate more to cognitive ergonomics. However, these aspects are equally important and should be considered likewise, for instance in training, implementation and further evaluation activities.

Regarding the expected benefits, participants see benefits if interactive robots and to some extent exoskeletons, significantly reduce manual, repetitive and strenuous tasks. Thus in the long-term leading to physical health improvements through a reduction of injuries and physical load. For exoskeletons, injury prevention and musculoskeletal benefits are seen in particular. The benefits of XR glasses stronger relate to training and planning aspects rather than supporting a variety of primary construction tasks.

The anticipated risks and challenges in the short- and long-term are mainly related to inter-active robots. Overall, the concerns revolve around safety, cost-effectiveness, worker acceptance, adaptability to diverse tasks and environments, and the need for proper training and support for the effective use of interactive robots. In the case of robots, the aspect of operating in unstructured environments, which is a feature of any construction site, is widely discussed. In addition, a strong barrier to efficient and fulfilling use is seen in the fact that most tasks require complex handling of materials and actions. A possible mitigation of these constraints is seen by deploying external actors (suppliers, system integrator etc.) to handle all programming and reconfiguring activities. Participants also raise the issue that additional attention might be required in order to operate

the robot. This aspect is also very closely related to the interaction design of the robotic system. Here designers should place particular emphasis on the principle of self-descriptiveness, so it is easily apparent, if some action from the operator is required or when the systems is operating in an autonomous mode. If the user needs to be involved, this needs to be made clear and transparent. Furthermore, participants bring the fear of job loss forward in some cases. This does somehow contrast the reluctance of many participants towards the robotics capabilities for being useful for different complex tasks as well as the expectations related to the interaction principle of *Suitability for the task*. Nevertheless, this matter has to be taken seriously and it is advisable to address this issue during the implementation process.

Foreseen risks and challenges related to exoskeletons mostly revolve around the issue of comfort and mobility as well as additional health and safety risks due to potential injuries if the exoskeleton gets caught somewhere on the construction site. Again, participants emphasise, that they see a very few tasks as being adequately supported by the technology and that especially the unstructured and non-standardised environment is a particular challenge.

6. Summary and next steps

In this deliverable we have presented the first results of HumanTech subjective assessment of the HumanTech wearables system and human-robot interactions. The results have been gathered from the organization of three different workshops in Spain and Ireland. Insights from the type of stakeholders identified (workers, apprentices and supervisors) have been analysed.

In conclusion, at this stage of familiarity with the three technologies the results indicate higher reluctance towards interactive robots than to exoskeletons and XR glasses mainly due to perceived low manoeuvrability, physical rigidity and sedateness. The synthesis of the expectations regarding the interaction principles as well as the qualitative material highlights the utmost importance of the interaction principle *Suitability for the tasks*, especially for experienced users. However, some results have to be considered carefully and thoroughly validated against feedback obtained from participants evaluating the actual use and interaction with the technologies, as foreseen at later stages of the HumanTech project. The results might differ greatly.

As shown the HumanTech architecture is a system of technological developments and in the coming months these technologies will be further designed and developed. We will be following this development close so that we can go on performing the subjective and objective assessment of those technological developments and reporting about it in the next version of this deliverable (D6.4) in M32. Planning for the next version includes:

- Organization of additional workshops in other countries to go on deeper in the subjective analysis (and thus complementing what has been done in T6.2)
- Performance of an objective assessment by the evaluation of physiological sensor data collected in dedicated training sessions. For doing so, technological developments of HumanTech wearables system and interactive and collaborative robot systems developed in WP4 and WP5 will have to be mature enough to be tested in pilots in WP7.

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Annex I: Example for workshop presentation

Current Context

Construction sector is an **important pillar** of the European economy.

Gross domestic product (GDP) of the total in EU is **9%** of the share.

In terms of employment, the sector provides **15-18 million direct jobs** in the EU, not counting indirect employment.

Construction Blueprint report shows that there are **many small enterprises** that operate in this industry.

All European countries are focusing on the **digitalization of the construction industry**

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Some activities in construction environment

Bridge inspection

Concrete application in buildings

Building demolition

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Main challenges facing construction

Solutions provided by HumanTech

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01 Collaborative & Interactive Robotics

Current situation in construction

Robotic systems as a vital part of automated production lines are normally isolated by physical barriers and workers are not allowed to be around

Traditional robotic system

Human robot collaborative scenario

A new concept of **collaborative robots** safer for workers to be around during operation, as they often have integrated mechanisms for safe stop when a collision is detected before serious damage is done to a worker or property

Multiple tasks monotonous, dangerous or little productive (e.g. transportation of materials from one place to another)

Workers transporting materials

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Solution proposed by interactive robotics

This technology allows for workers and robots sharing the task and executing it together at the same time

Human robot collaborative scenario

Collaborative robots example

Drawback : cobots still require significant advanced training to be operated and robot programming time can be a bottleneck for efficiency

Development of intuitive communication channels (as speech, gestures, etc.) between robot and worker can significantly contribute to efficient deployment of cobots in construction sites

Human robot multimodal interaction

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Benefits of Interactive robotics

- ❑ Robotic technology can contribute to:
 - Execution of supporting task (e.g., brick hand-over) allowing the worker to concentrate on core-competence tasks
 - Execution of physically difficult tasks (e.g., moving heavy loads)
 - Execution of time-consuming repetitive tasks (e.g., material handling)

- ❑ Collaborative and interactive robotics allows for:
 - Workers can safely work close to the robots
 - Workers can use normal language and intuitive gestures for giving robots simple commands, no advanced robotic training required
 - Workers understand behaviour of the robot and are comfortable working with robots
 - Robots behave in a predictable manner

Interactive robotics helping human

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02 Exoskeleton technologies

Current situation in construction

Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) are the most common work-related health problem in Europe

Several risk factors are involved in the production of MSDs, which are related to the task and to the organisation of work: manual handling of loads, forced static or dynamic postures, repetitive movements, etc.

Musculoskeletal symptoms in working bricklayers

Workers constructing a brick wall

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Constructing a brick wall is a repetitive procedure in which part of the work is carried out in awkward postures, for example, when the work is done over shoulder height (being the shoulders and elbows the main affected body areas).

Solution proposed by exoskeleton technologies

In recent years, exoskeletons have been proposed as the solution to all the problems associated with WMSDs

Lightweight integrated body sensor in exoskeleton solutions for construction workers, to help them in:

- ❑ Carrying heavy material or lifting intelligently while the body sensors can warn them about straining or having bad poses during tasks
- ❑ Avoiding muscle-skeletal disorders due to repetitive movements

Worker helped by an exoskeleton

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Benefits of Humantech exoskeleton

- ❑ The exoskeleton would assist the wearer in its task ...
 - Reducing the muscular activity of the assisted areas
 - Preventing from adopting risk postures

Situations with ENABLED exoskeleton

Situations with DISABLED exoskeleton

- ❑ ... without impeding other movements involved in the tasks
 - the exoskeleton anticipates and adapts to the needs of the user in each task and,
 - the exoskeleton gets out of the way when it is not needed

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03 eXtended Reality technologies

Current situation in construction

- ❖ Visualization of 3D objects in a 2D screen of a laptop/tablet. CAD Drawing leading to misinformed CAD data
- ❖ Insufficient construction data and information available to the worker leading to inefficient decision making and errors
- ❖ Worker training scenarios in dangerous and unsafe on-site locations

Construction planning on 2D diagram

Worker training in dangerous on-site locations

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Solution proposed by XR technologies

- ❖ Extended reality (XR) is a computer-based technology that adds virtual content to the real-world environment.
- ❖ Using XR glasses like Microsoft Hololen2, 3D models and 2D elements like texts are superimposed onto the real world.
- ❖ In HumanTech, XR technology will be used for:
 - Visualization
 - Interaction with 3D models
 - Training of workers in safe and remote environments

XR technologies for superimposed content

Example of XR Glasses

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Benefits of XR technologies

- ❑ Different XR functions are:
 - Visualizing 3D objects
 - Provide a user interface
 - Work over 3D holograms or multi-user collaboration

XR used in construction sites

XR Glasses providing additional information

Engineers and industrial designers can visualize and collaborate with CAD data in an Augmented Reality environment

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Annex II: Questionnaires for stakeholders

Questionnaires for apprentices / workers

Focus groups

Date: 06/13/2023

PARTICIPANT CODE: HT-002-_____

Demographic Information

Please, complete this demographic information:

Your range of age:

- 25 or less
- Between 26 and 35
- Between 36 and 45
- Between 46 and 55
- More than 56

Your gender:

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary

How many years of experience do you have in the construction sector?

- 5 or less
- From 6 to 10
- More than 10

Your position:

- Apprentice
- Worker
- Responsible person / Engineer / OSH manager

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Please answer the following questions (choose only one option by statement):

Statement	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
I like to look more closely at technical systems.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I like to try out the functions of new technical systems.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is enough for me that a technical system works, I don't care how or why.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is enough for me to know the basic functions of a technical system.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Collaborative Robots

Please rate the following statements (choose only one of the options per statement):

Statement	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	No idea (6)
The cobot will support my task.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The handling of the cobot will be easy to learn.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The specific functions of the cobot will be self-explaining.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will be able to control the actions of the cobot at any time.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will always know what every function of the cobot can be used for.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Operator errors will not lead to serious consequences.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will be able to adapt the cobot to my own needs and abilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Please order the following statements from most to least important (from 1 to 9, use each number only once):

Statement	Order
I need to have visual info of the status of the cobot (such as the current movement that is performing) as well as of its next steps, with emphasis on ensuring safe operation.	
I would like to use tactile screens to interact with the cobot.	
I would like to use gestures to interact with the cobot.	
I would like to use augmented reality to interact with the cobot.	
I would like to have control over the work rate (e.g. including the option to increase or decrease the speed as needed).	
For guaranteeing trust, I think it is important to detect the presence of workers near the cobots, and their distance to avoid accidents or problems.	
The cobot should adapt to my specific preferences and skills to provide me the most suitable help in each moment.	
Prior to introducing a new interactive robotic system, I would like to have a specified in-depth training.	
I would like to be aware if and what type of data is collected by the robotic system and for what purpose.	

Please answer the following open-ended questions from your perspective:

How do you think your task will change by using the cobot?

Do you expect benefits from using the cobot (in the short- and long-term)? Which ones?

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Where do you see potential problems when using the cobot (in the short- and long-term)? Which ones?

Empty response area for the first question.

Which options would I like to be able to configure in a cobot? (e.g. speed)

Empty response area for the second question.

I can imagine to work with a cobot, especially when

Empty response area for the third question.

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Exoskeletons

Please rate the following statements (choose only one of the options per statement):

Statement	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	No idea (6)
The exoskeleton will support my task.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The handling of the exoskeleton will be easy to learn.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The specific functions of the exoskeleton will be self-explaining.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will be able to control the actions of the exoskeleton at any time.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will always know what every function of the exoskeleton can be used for.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Operator errors will not lead to serious consequences.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will be able to adapt the exoskeleton to my own needs and abilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Please order the following statements from most to least important (from 1 to 8, use each number only once):

Statement	Order
If I do not have any physical problems, I do not think I need it.	
I would wear it, independently of my age.	
I think if it takes me more than ten minutes to correctly adjust the system, that is too much time I lose.	
It is important that I can move freely wearing it and it doesn't hinder me.	
I need to be fast in my work, so I need something that I can move really fast with.	
The exoskeleton should be comfortable (not scratch, press or pull anywhere), light and unobtrusive. If it is not comfortable, then I do not like to wear it.	
I work on open spaces depending on the weather, so I cannot imagine wearing it in in bad weather and environmental conditions such as dirt, water, rain or extreme temperature.	
I would like exoskeletons to be easy to clean and the possibility for sterilization.	

Please answer the following open-ended questions from your perspective:

How do you think your task will change by using the exoskeleton?

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Do you expect benefits from using the exoskeleton (in the short- and long-term)? Which ones?

Empty response area for the first question.

Where do you see potential problems when using the exoskeleton (in the short- and long-term)? Which ones?

Empty response area for the second question.

I can imagine to wear the exoskeleton, especially when ...

Empty response area for the third question.

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

RX Technologies

Please rate the following statements (choose only one of the options per statement):

Statement	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	No idea (6)
The XR glasses will support my task.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The handling of the XR glasses will be easy to learn.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The specific functions of the XR glasses will be self-explaining.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will be able to control the actions of the XR glasses at any time.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will always know what every function of the XR glasses can be used for.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Operator errors will not lead to serious consequences.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I will be able to adapt the XR glasses to my own needs and abilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Please order the following statements from most to least important (from 1 to 10, use each number only once):

Statement	Order
It is important that the system provides remote / virtual assistants for learning and training during work.	
I would like to have visual info of the system status, and/or the next operational steps, with emphasis on ensuring safe operation.	
I would like to use augmented reality to interact with the system.	
I consider it useful to receive warning messages suggesting an easy way to recover from errors.	
The system should communicate with me graphically rather than textually.	
If I need to wear a helmet at work, I would like the XR glasses being attached to the helmet.	
I would like to be introduced to the technology in detail by means of instruction before my first contact with XR glasses.	
I would like XR glasses to offer the possibility of easily adjusting contrast, sharpness and luminance to my needs.	
If I am working with XR glasses for several hours, I would like to have frequent short breaks to take off the device.	
I would like a well-balanced weight of the XR glasses in order not to have compensatory muscle activity or fatigue.	

Please answer the following open-ended questions from your perspective:

How do you think your task will change by using XR glasses?

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Do you expect benefits from using the XR glasses (in the short- and long-term)? Which ones?

Empty response area for the first question.

Where do you see potential problems when using the XR glasses (in the short- and long-term)? Which ones?

Empty response area for the second question.

I can imagine to wear the XR glasses, especially when

Empty response area for the third question.

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Questionnaires for responsible person / supervisor

Focus groups

Date: 06/13/2023

PARTICIPANT CODE: HT-003-_____

Demographic Information

Please, complete this demographic information:

Your range of age:

- 25 or less
- Between 26 and 35
- Between 36 and 45
- Between 46 and 55
- More than 56

Your gender:

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary

How many years of experience do you have in the construction sector?

- 5 or less
- From 6 to 10
- More than 10

Your position:

- Apprentice
- Worker
- Responsible person / Engineer / OSH manager

HumanTech project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101058236

Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Please answer the following questions (choose only one option by statement):

Statement	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
I like to look more closely at technical systems.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I like to try out the functions of new technical systems.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is enough for me that a technical system works, I don't care how or why.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
It is enough for me to know the basic functions of a technical system.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Focus Groups · 13th July 2023

Collaborative Robots

Please rate the following statements (choose only one of the options per statement):

Statement	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	No idea (6)
I believe the implementation of cobots in a company like Acciona is beneficial.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I believe it is sensible that the company invests in cobots.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I believe the workforce will be openminded towards cobots.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Please answer the following open-ended questions from your perspective:

Do you expect benefits from using the cobot (in the short- and long-term)? Which ones?

Where do you see potential problems when using the cobot (in the short- and long-term)?

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From your perspective, what are the most important resources needed for a successful implementation of cobots?

Empty response area for the first question.

Which department do you see in the lead for a successful cobot implementation?

Empty response area for the second question.

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Exoskeletons

Please rate the following statements (choose only one of the options per statement):

Statement	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	No idea (6)
I believe the implementation of exoskeletons in a company like Acciona is beneficial.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I believe it is sensible that the company invests in exoskeletons.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I believe the workforce will be openminded towards exoskeletons.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Please answer the following open-ended questions from your perspective:

Do you expect benefits from using the exoskeleton (in the short- and long-term)?
Which ones?

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Where do you see potential problems when using the exoskeleton (in the short- and long-term)?

[Empty response area for the first question]

From your perspective, what are the most important resources needed for a successful implementation of exoskeletons?

[Empty response area for the second question]

Which department do you see in the lead for a successful exoskeleton implementation?

[Empty response area for the third question]

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RX Technologies

Please rate the following statements (choose only one of the options per statement):

Statement	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	No idea (6)
I believe the implementation of XR glasses in a company like Acciona is beneficial.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I believe it is sensible that the company invests in XR glasses.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I believe the workforce will be openminded towards XR glasses.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Please answer the following open-ended questions from your perspective:

Do you expect benefits from using the XR glasses (in the short- and long-term)? Which ones?

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Where do you see potential problems when using the XR glasses (in the short- and long-term)?

[Empty response area for the first question]

From your perspective what are the most important resources needed for a successful implementation of XR glasses?

[Empty response area for the second question]

Which department do you see in the lead for a successful XR glasses implementation?

[Empty response area for the third question]

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Annex III: Informed Consent document

Consent Form for the participation in research in the framework of "Human Centered Technologies for a Safer and Greener European Construction Industry (HumanTech, HT)"

Thank you for agreeing to participate and help in our research! To take part in the research, we need your consent to the collection and processing of your personal data. For this reason, the purpose of this form is to inform you in detail about the research and the issues concerning your personal data. At the end, you will find two forms which, if you choose to do so, you can use to provide us with your consent to participate in the HumanTech project we are inviting you to join.

A. General Information on the Research

The European construction industry faces three major challenges: improve its productivity, increase the safety and wellbeing of its workforce and make a shift towards a green, resource efficient industry. To address these challenges adequately, the European research project (funded by the European Commission) HumanTech proposes a human-centered approach, involving innovative technologies such as wearables for worker safety and support, and intelligent robotic technology that can harmoniously co-exist with human workers while also contributing to the green transition of the industry.

The purpose of the HumanTech project is **to study in detail the use of innovative technologies in construction industry and in particular the factors in relation to a human-centred integration and use. In addition, the research shall seek to investigate any consequences for construction site workers, in terms of the application and their interaction with the technologies and the further development of design recommendations for these technologies.**

The aim of the research is to gain insights from construction site workers on their perception of the HumanTech technologies. This will be done through participation of construction site workers at an early stage of the project. We are interested in the insights workers can give from their point of view on the HumanTech technologies.

The expected results of research can be summarised in the benefits of collecting reliable data and writing an in-depth study. These results will be included in the HumanTech project in order to further develop and design the different technologies.

The surveys, data and conclusions will be used as a tool for identifying areas of improvement and action areas in relation to the HumanTech technologies.

1. How will you take part in the survey?

To take part in the survey you must give your consent by filling in the relevant forms that follow. **Before you decide you can ask us anything you want, and we can also provide any additional information and/or clarification. Participation is not compulsory, and you can change your mind and stop your participation at any time.**

2. Is there any reward/incentive for participation?

Participation in HumanTech project is voluntary.

3. Is there any cost?

There is no cost of participation.

4. Who can participate?

Any construction site worker identified by the HumanTech industry partners. The worker participation might focus on some defined worker groups like on-site workers only, or team-leader only.

5. How will the research be conducted?

The research will either be done on-site at the premises of the HumanTech industry partners or in form of an online workshop. After a short introduction to the HumanTech project and the HumanTech technologies (interactive robots, exoskeletons and XR technologies) the workers will be asked to answer some standardized questions on a survey. Also, an open discussion in relation to the potential use of these technologies will be promoted. On behalf of the HumanTech project the specific research in relation to worker participation will be led by the research partner Fundacion Tecnalia Research & Innovation (TEC) and in terms of question development and data analysis supported by the research partner German Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA)

6. What will we ask you?

All the questions will be in relation to the potential use of the HumanTech technologies and your working tasks in the construction industry. We will focus for example on your personal expectations in relation to the technologies like expected risks but also benefits.

You can refuse to answer any questions you don't want, ask the coordinator for a break whenever you want to, or terminate the procedure completely without any consequence and without having to explain why.

7. What are the benefits of participation?

There is no direct benefit from participating in the research. However, the participation of workers in this study helps researcher to better design innovative technologies.

8. What are the potential risks of participation?

There are no anticipated, specific, or even potential risks of participation. Special attention has been taken to ensure that the topics of discussion and related questions have no negative impact on participants. Nevertheless, the members of the research team responsible for the HumanTech project will be ready to deal with any situation.

9. How will the information from the HumanTech project be used and who will have access to it?

The data collected through the HumanTech project will only be used for the purposes of the research within the project. More specifically, the information and data collected by the research partners TEC and BAuA will be used to draw conclusions that will help to provide a more complete and in-depth understanding of the effects the HumanTech technologies may have on construction workers. In addition, this research will seek to investigate any consequences for the participants experiencing this kind of new technologies.

The conclusions drawn **without your or other participants' personal data** will be used to draw useful conclusions and to write an in-depth study. The anonymized study results will be used in a scientific context and a project report.

It may also be used in the form of statistical data for internal presentations and progress presentations on the project, as well as in the context of progress and research presentations within a scientific or practitioners related context. Anonymized data might be used for the preparation of articles for scientific journals and for conference

presentations.

10. What about the collected personal data?

You can find information about your personal data in section B of this document (Collection and processing of Personal Data in the Research).

11. Can I access the results of the research?

Of course! You can ask us to send you the results and additional information by sending an e-mail to Ms. Sara Sillaurren (sara.sillaurren@tecnalia.com) or Ms. Patricia Rosen (rosen.patricia@baua.bund.de).

12. Do you have any other questions?

You can ask anything you want directly to the members of our research team organizing the worker participation within the HumanTech project before the procedure starts.

13. The scientific coordinators the research

The early worker participation within the HumanTech project is led and coordinated by the research partner TEC. TEC is responsible for the collection, handling and storage of all data (personal and research data). The research partner BAuA has contributed to the design of the specific questions and is together with TEC responsible for the data analysis.

- Research partner Fundacion Tecnalia Research & Innovation (TEC): Parque Tecnológico de San Sebastián, Mikeletegi Pasealekua, 2 E-20009 DONOSTIA-SAN SEBASTIÁN (Spain)
- Research partner German Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA): Friedrich-Henkel-Weg 1-25, 44149 Dortmund (Germany)

14. Contact data

If you have any questions, you can contact the scientific coordinators of the project, who in this context have the role of main consultants.

Ms. Sara Sillaurren (sara.sillaurren@tecnalia.com) or **Ms. Patricia Rosen** (rosen.patricia@baua.bund.de)

B. Collection and processing of Personal Data in the Research

1. Introduction

In this section you will find all information regarding the collection and processing of participants' personal data in the research. After reading the section you can ask questions and request more information about the topic from our research team members.

Please do not give your consent until you have read and understood this section, or before you have received adequate answers to your questions or queries.

2. Who is in charge for the processing of your personal data?

Denomination: Fundación TECNALIA Research and Innovation (TECNALIA)

Address: Parque Tecnológico de San Sebastián, Mikeletegi Pasealekua,2 E-20009 DONOSTIA-SAN SEBASTIÁN (España)

Telephone: 902760000

VAT: G48975767

Email: dpo@tecnalia.com

3. Who is in charge for the processing of your anonymized research data?

Denomination: German Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA)

Address: Friedrich-Henkel-Weg 1-25, 44149 Dortmund (Germany)

Telephone: +49 231 9071-1971

VAT: DE 124 652 539

Email: rosen.patricia@baua.bund.de

4. What is the legal basis for the processing of your data?

The processing of your data is based on your consent, expressed through this document and with a revocable nature, at any later time. In any case, said consent will be understood to be freely granted, expressly stating that the lack of consent for one or all of the purposes, or its subsequent revocation, will not entail any consequence for the interested parties.

5. What type of data we collect, for what purpose and how we use it

i. Personal data

Full name, range of age, gender, position in the company and technology perception; Research data: subjective ratings on expectation towards HumanTech technologies, interaction quality and technology acceptance in relation to the deployed technologies. The purpose of the processing will be to obtain information about your perception of HumanTech technologies and its subsequent analysis in order to achieve the objectives of the project.

ii. Data from the consent form

Your full name and signature will be collected through the consent and forms. This will be the only information that will directly allow for your identification and is collected based on our obligation by law to seek your consent to participate in research and your consent to the collection and processing of your personal data, and our obligation to be able to demonstrate that we have obtained that consent.

We do not process or use the data for any other purpose. **We will only use the data if we need to show them for evidential purposes at the request of the European Commission and they will be placed in a separate storage file.** In addition, they are not linked in any way to the alphanumeric participant code, so that they cannot be linked to your answers and associated notes by the research team, in order to protect and maintain your anonymity.

iii. Data collected through photographs, videos and voice recordings

As a consequence of your participation in events related to the project, the production of audiovisual material for the dissemination of project activities is planned. This may entail taking photographs, recordings in which you appear. The data object of treatment would be image and voice.

Personal data will only be processed in accordance with the purposes described and will not be used for profiling or automated decision-making.

3. Who has access to this data, where it is kept and for how long

- Full names will be used to record participant's informed consent and data privacy statements.
- The personal data will only be processed by TEC and BAuA employees entrusted with the implementation of the project.
- Personal data collection is done either by written self-disclosure, interviews or participatory observation.
- The personal data will only be processed according to the given purpose. A subsequent use or transfer to third parties will not be done, except by legal obligation.
- Your personal data will not be published.
- The personal data **will be deleted** after the purpose of use has ceased, but at the latest by the end of the HumanTec project (31st May 2025)
- The research data is **collected in written form**. These forms will be digitalized and stored in secure servers of Tecnia (where uniquely the researchers participating in HumanTech will have access). These data will be pseudonymized and provided to BAuA, who will be in charge of processing them by aggregating answers and obtain conclusions referred to all the participants preferences related to presented technologies.

4. How do we protect your data?

In any case, the collection and processing of personal data in the context of the HumanTech project is always in accordance with the applicable legislation, and the rules of ethics and ethics regarding the protection of personal data and respect for privacy. Specifically, in the context of this research, in accordance with the legislation on privacy and personal data protection, we have taken all necessary and appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure the protection of personal data. We have established policies and procedures for the protection of personal data, and all members of our research team are aware of their obligation to protect personal data and have received relevant training and are bound by confidentiality clauses and the principles of scientific ethics.

5. Rights of individuals

The law gives you certain specific rights regarding your personal data, which our research team fully respects and will help you to exercise them at any time. In particular, you have the right to:

- i. The right to be informed / transparency: You have the right to know who is processing your data, what categories of data they are using and why. The organisations processing your data must give you clear information in plain language (for more details see Articles 12, 13 and 14 of the GDPR).
- ii. The right of access: You have the right to request access to your personal data that an organisation has about you (for more details see Article 15 of the GDPR). You can exercise this right free of charge in most cases by making an access request in writing or verbally, if you wish to.
- iii. The right to rectification: You have the right to have the data rectified, if your data is inaccurate and/or incomplete (for more details see Articles 16 & 19 of the GDPR).
- iv. The right to erasure ('right to be forgotten'): You have the right to have your personal data erased under specific conditions, such as where your data is no longer necessary, you have withdrawn your consent, your data has been unlawfully processed etc. (for more details see Articles 17 & 19 of the GDPR).

- v. The right to restriction of processing: You have the right to obtain restriction of processing where the accuracy of your personal data is contested, the processing is unlawful, the controller no longer needs the personal data for the purposes of the processing, you have objected to automated processing (for more details see Articles 18 and 19 of the GDPR).
- vi. The right to data portability: You have the right to have your data transmitted to another data controller (for more information see Article 20 of the GDPR).
- vii. The right to object: You have the right to object to the processing of your personal data by an organisation, provided that this is not contrary to the public interest (for more details see Article 21 of the GDPR).
- viii. The right to human intervention: You have the right to object where a decision is based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning you or significantly affects you (for more details see Article 22 of the GDPR).
- ix. The right to file a complaint. If you have any questions, concerns or complaints about how we process and use your personal data, you can contact us. We hope we can answer any questions you may have and resolve any issues that may arise. However, you also have the right to lodge a complaint with the relevant data protection authorities. For more information and how to make a complaint, you can visit the Data Protection Authority's website (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/2016-05-04>).

To exercise these rights or for any other question related to the protection of your data, you must contact TECNALIA through the e-mail and telephone number provided in the section 2 Who is in charge for the processing of your data?

Consent for the processing of personal data in the context of participation in the research of the HumanTech project

Date: 06/13/2023

PARTICIPANT CODE: HT-003-_____

I, the undersigned _____, after reading and understanding what is indicated in Section B of the attached information form regarding the collection and processing of personal data, give my authorization to the entities listed in point 2 of the same document (joint controller), for the use, retransmission or reproduction of sequences filmed on video, photographs or voice recordings of my person due to my presence in events and activities of the project object of diffusion being informed that there is no time limit on the validity of this authorization; nor is there any geographic specification as to where it can be viewed. Having read and understood the accompanying information form and having received answers to all questions and queries, declare that

- I consent to the processing of my personal data to obtain information about my perception of HumanTech technologies.
- I consent to the processing of my personal data for the dissemination of audiovisual material (pictures and video) captured in the sales of the project for scientific dissemination purposes.

[Signature]

_____/_____/_____